

Employability and Work Environment as Predictors to Employee Productivity of Banks Employees

Marites D. Paquibulan, MBA¹ & Stilo Floyd Schneider, PHD., DBA, CGSP, CHIA²

¹Teacher II of Monkayo National High School-Senior High & ²Professor of UM Tagum College

Abstract: The main purpose of this study was to find out if employability and work environment significantly influence employee productivity of banks employees of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro. The 255 respondents of this study are from 27 banks of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro. The statistical tools used to interpret the data gathered were Mean, Pearson-r, and Multiple Regression Analysis. The independent variables were employability and work environment, while the dependent variable was employee productivity. Findings from the study revealed that employability got a mean of 4.33 which means very high. This indicates that the level of employability is very much observed. And, work environment received a mean of 4.20 which means very high, this indicates that the level of work environment is very much observed. On the other hand, employee productivity got a mean score of 4.31 which means very high, this indicates that the level of employee productivity is very much observed. Moreover, the result shows a significant relationship between employability and work environment on employee productivity. Also, all the domains of the variables mentioned above significantly predict the employee productivity of bank employees of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro. Thus, a better employability and work environment would positively contribute to increasing employee productivity.

Keywords: *Banking Industry, Employability, Work Environment, and Employee Productivity, Philippines*

I. INTRODUCTION

The major problem of the banking industry is finding new ways to improve employee productivity. Any employee challenges, such as company culture, personal attributes, and interpersonal relationships, naturally affect employees' productivity. Employees' emotional and physical health can be harmed by any circumstances that bring them stress. Their work suffers as a result, and their capacity to perform at their best is harmed. Employees' productivity fails when they are distracting and unhappy. That is why organizations need to focus on examining what factors predict the employee productivity of banks' employees (Ibrahim, 2021).

In today's economy, employee productivity is essential in organizations. Employees may be encouraged to be competitive and productive if organizations strategize how to hire, train, and reward them (Longnecker & Fink, 2001). Employee productivity is the newest strategy in the organization. They anchored the idea that this relationship is crucial because a business can use its human resources to gain a competitive advantage by enhancing productivity. Because once employees are productive, the operating income increases, the company expands, and the workers are rewarded with incentives. It is growing the business to where the employees and employers are satisfying (Onyije, 2015).

However, banks must uphold employability and a pleasant working environment to ensure employee productivity. Employability is linked to enhancing employee productivity. Employees that are highly employable are likely to be top achievers, and employability can help a company achieve exceptional results and maintain competitiveness (Nepangue-Seaman et al., 2016). Also, a healthy working environment is essential for ensuring employee productivity and avoiding undue stress, adversely affecting job efficiency. The work environment is the sum of the inter-relationships between employees and the working environment. Thus, the issues of organizational employability and work environment predict employee productivity (Al-Omari & Okasheh, 2017).

The researcher has not come across a study conducted in line with the employability and work environment as predictors of employee productivity of banks' employees. The researcher observed that some banks employees rant about organizational issues regarding employee productivity. Like how co-employees behave and perform within the

organization depends on their employability, how they interact with other employees, immediate supervisors, and even clients, and the work environment. Employability and work environment are great contributors to employee productivity and success of the banking industry, with the belief that this research study could contribute towards improving the employee productivity of the banks' employees of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro, thus the urgency to conduct the study.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This section contains theories, concepts, facts, information, opinions, and readings about employability, work environment, and employee productivity.

2.1 Employability

Employability is the first independent variable. Employability is having a unique ability, experience, individual attributes, and characteristics that can realize job opportunities that benefit them, their co-workers, the organization, and the industry. Can adjust to ever-develop, demanding organizational and career environment, which has psychological and social aspects. Individuals with high levels of employability can sustain employment (Vargas-Hernandez & Jimenez, 2015).

Employability is defined and described worldwide. *Openness to changes at work*, as evidenced by the lengthy and complicated history of employability research. Employees that are flexible to change, willing to adapt, and consciously aware of the potential of change in diverse settings are receptive to changes at work. Open people appear to be more flexible and believe that the change will benefit them. Individuals who are willing to try new things and innovation are more adaptive to changing work and life contexts, which improves their employability (Augustsson et al. 2017).

Employability has emerged as the first foundation of global demand, enhancing employee participation in the labor market while remaining appealing and employable in today's dynamic and unpredictable workplace. The world of work has changed, and *work and career proactivity* are essential given this change. Work and career proactivity entail deliberately controlling oneself and surroundings to make things happen. It entails wishing for and working for progressive transition to create a different and more desirable future (Wang & Parker, 2015).

Recent literature includes *career motivation* as an indicator of employability. *Career motivation* refers to a person's determination to put as much effort as feasible to make effective job decisions. Employees passionate about their jobs are eager to take advantage of the development and advancement possibilities provided by transformative leaders. Because they establish workplace environments that encourage the development and practice of new talents that may promote career progression, transformational leaders impact their colleagues' career success (Baethge et al., 2017).

Moreover, research has shown that something positively related to various employability measures to *work and career resilience*. Work and career resilience are complex phenomena that describe a person's ability to cope in a high-pressure circumstance. Employee resilience refers to an employee's ability to utilize resources to continue adjusting and prospering at work, even in adversity, as encouraged and supported by the business. Employees with a high level of career resilience should expect to work independently, take the initiative, and proactively seek to improve their work-related skills and knowledge. Employees like this help businesses achieve a long-term competitive advantage in the global marketplace (Tien & Wang, 2017).

Despite a comprehensive view of employability, Jabbar et al. (2019) focused attention on *optimism at work* as an indicator of employability. The core themes of optimistic psychology are optimism at work, a positive mental attitude toward future events, and the self. Those optimistic at work are more likely to take positive actions in the face of future challenges and have self-assurance in their capabilities to overcome objective, practical challenges and improve employability.

There is also literature that describes employability as associated with *work identity*. Work identity is a multifaceted job consciousness that integrates levels of workplace aspects of an individual's self-image. When people conduct work, their other identities influence their practices and behaviors. As a result, work identity promotes employability by providing inspiration, direction, and purpose to career-related endeavors (Fabio, 2017).

Evidence of broader interpretations of employability, such as continuous learning, job enrichment, and management educational development, are all critical aspects of organizational development. Self-empowerment and productive networking are also necessary to improve and retain employment at all stages of life. Employability is a lifelong commitment in competitive and beneficial in ensuring that it does not end when a person retires. Employability is a continuous self-evaluation process and assessment of one's abilities (Herbert, 2016).

Finally, literature illustrates that employability is the unique mix of skills, abilities, resilience, positive outlook, and personal attributes. A person with a broad range of experiences earned through advanced education is more likely to find work that they enjoy and excel in. As indicated by the continuous and innovative development of employability study, employability has been defined and characterized locally and internationally, including flexibility, adaptability, skills, competencies, and knowledge. Experiences shape individuals to become more employable and work productivity. It implies increasing employment (Baciu et al., 2016).

2.2 Work Environment

The second independent variable is the work environment. The work environment context, social characteristics, and physical conditions wherein you accomplish your job. These factors can affect emotions of well-being, relationships with co-workers, teamwork, productivity, and wellness programs. External structure, a company's culture, and workplace conditions are a work environment's three most important characteristics. Determine your personality traits and values by looking at your work environment (Career Guide, 2020).

Many work environment studies have shown it satisfied workers regarding *decision latitude*. Decision latitude is one's feeling of control over decision-making in the workplace, including control over the use of abilities, intellectual competence, organizational characteristics, freedom, time commitment, and individual schedule flexibility. High decision latitude at work is a job resource that allows employees to learn new abilities and put them to use, which is essential for the experience of a dynamic learning environment and collaborative sharing of ideas at work. Such latitude can directly affect productivity (Ziaee et al., 2019).

One aspect of the work environment is *psychological demands*. Psychological demands, as physiological, interpersonal, or institutional aspects of the job that employees must meet to maintain physical and mental effort. It related the conditions of employment to how hard a person works. High psychological expectations can strain an employee's ability to execute their job effectively and cause them to lack confidence in their abilities and skills, dissatisfaction with their work, and low productivity (Wanjira et al., 2020).

In recent research, *supervisor social support* has recently identified as an essential determinant of the work environment. Emotional support, appraisal support, informational support, and physical support are four major psychological dimensions of supervisor social support. Leaders recognize their employees' accomplishments and care for their well-being. Because supporting acts by a supervisor build employee belief or anticipations for future benefit receipts, supervisor support also leads to employee motivation for positive reciprocity (Collins et al., 2016).

Fortunately, strong *co-worker social support* improves the work environment by relieving employee stress and enhancing job satisfaction and performance. Co-worker social support means aiding one another in their jobs when expertise and knowledge are needed and bringing motivation and encouragement. It is inadequate to reach the company's goals when there is a conflict between co-workers. Co-worker social support is significant in the work environment to maintain a productive working relationship among workers and be a valuable team member (Raziqa&Maulabakhsh, 2015).

In most previous studies, the work environment is where the workers perform tasks and work every day. Supervisors have positive relationships with their colleagues, receive training and development, have an attractive, quick incentive and reward scheme, and have an appropriate workload. When employees have a positive attitude toward work and everything in the environment, they achieve their goals. They can positively affect employee performance development and influence work better so that productivity is at the maximum level (Awan & Tahir, 2015).

Finally, the research shows that a work environment is a setting in which workers operate in a company that can influence employees' physical and psychological conditions, which can affect their productivity, either directly or indirectly. If people perform optimally, peacefully, and efficiently, we can say the work atmosphere is favorable. As a result, the organization must foster a sense of belonging, open communication, and self-control in order to achieve shared objectives. Workplace benefits include instilling a desire to work, resulting in increased productivity and performance (Sitohong, 2020).

2.3 Employee Productivity

The dependent variable in this study is employee productivity. We consider employees as the best assets of a company and the headspring of the core competence. Nowadays, the banking sectors want to develop ways to keep employees contributing to their full potential, fully motivate the initiative for work, and make the employees work product in the organization. The company invests in training and other forms of personal development for its personnel to gain capital appreciation through increased employee productivity. Hence, employee productivity is a metric that measures both the workforce's efficiency and effectiveness(Harness, 2018).

Employee productivity, often known as *efficiency*, the efficiency of a worker or a group of workers is measured. Efficiency refers to the extent to which something is efficient. Efficiency implies that they make the most of their working hours to create more and better products in less time. They complete their job and achieve a fair number of tasks. It demonstrates that they stick to schedules, make fewer mistakes, are cost-efficient, and do not spend too much time on a particular charge. The efficiency of an organization's staff is critical to its success, and it is an essential factor to consider (Hanaysha; 2016).

Additionally, employee productivity has directly affected the company's profits and condition. Employees need to produce valuable and *quality* work. Quality refers to creating products or services that meet and exceed customer requirements and expectations, then the customers' satisfaction. Therefore, an employee's productivity is the quantity of output and the production quality and measures the goal achievement (Salimi, 2015).

In most employees' productivity, *timeliness* is an essential element of the overall order. Employee productivity is the time an employee spends producing the desired outputs. The expectation of information accessibility and availability in a reasonable amount of time is timeliness. Furthermore, the timeliness element assesses whether a task was completed accurately and on time. When the output is readily available, an employer can determine an employee's timeliness. Timeliness is critical for maintaining customer satisfaction and long-term loyalty and motivating employees to do their best work and productivity and strengthening your company's market position (Mutuku&Nyaribo, 2015).

Past literature reveals that employee productivity can measure through the *effectiveness* of an employee. Looks at the quality of the results we achieve and to which something is successful in producing the desired result. A successful worker not only strives to complete assignments as quickly as possible but also to solve problems creatively and consistently improve their efficiency to produce the best results. Therefore, the effectiveness of employee measures regularly meets targets and aims to do high-quality work (Okeke et al., 2016).

It is hard to find a precise definition of an employee's productivity. Employee productivity is the most effective use of all skills, resources, and competencies to improve the quality and quantity of work while reducing waste and allowing people to enjoy better lives outside of work. They can also gain skills and information that will keep them employable for the rest of their lives, resulting in increased employee productivity, which leads to competitiveness and human progress (Saatchi, 2017).

Lastly, the goal of every company is to boost employee productivity. Employee productivity increases bring several benefits to both the company and its employees. Increased productivity boosts an organization's edge over its competitors by lowering costs and increasing massive production. Similarly, employers may reward highly productive staff with higher compensation and better job chances. As a result, examining its determinants is integral to maintaining organizational sustainability and long-term performance (Baily et al., 2015).

2.4 Correlation between Measures

People today are hard to find a job even if they are degree holders. They are most likely to be competing against others, especially if they have the same academic qualifications. But suppose you have a particular combination of personal characteristics, abilities, ideals, and the ability to put them into practice once they've gained some experience. In that case, you will make you stand out from the crowd, referring to employability. The researcher stated that employability is not just about getting a job but also about being successful throughout their working life. The result showed that employers' primary concern is to hire highly employable employees because they are top achievers, and employability may require the organization to achieve exceptional results and sustain competitiveness. Therefore, employability and employee productivity are related to individuals and the organization (Yorke, 2019).

Employment opportunities are limited, and not everyone gets a job. Employability is becoming a central mission and forcefully promoted in business. Individuals require enhancement of their employability to gain an income and essential for employment survival. Employability means the capability to gain employment, hold it, and, if necessary, find another job. Also, employability cites a person's opportunity to secure and stay at the work they like. Employability is a series of experiences that make a person a high-performing individual. Results endorsed that employability attributes can enhance employee productivity in the workplace and benefit society and an organization. Meaning employability is positively related to employee productivity (McCowan, 2015).

Meanwhile, an issue of productivity is not only focused on employability but also the work environment. The work environment significantly influences how you feel about your job. Employees feel good about coming to work in a positive work environment, which motivates them to keep them going throughout the day. That's why employers should create a positive atmosphere and consistently encourage their employees; these correlate with improving happiness, and motivation, improving morale, fostering growth, promoting collaboration, and increasing employee productivity. Based on the findings, employees need a suitable working environment to do their jobs correctly and to the best of their abilities (Sumiyati et al., 2016).

The work environment always significantly influences anyone, including the company, and should gain more attention. Employers should take the initiative in improving the work environment so that employees will be motivated. The researcher found that the work environment substantially impacts employees' well-being and develops interaction, collaboration, innovation, and job satisfaction. Employees will attain the required outputs and goals, and productivity will grow. The work environment impacts the quality of an employee's job and their level of productivity (Al-Omari & Okasheh, 2017).

The above literature readings illustrate a definite association between employability, work environment, and employee productivity, and how it touches the productivity of the organizations critically supports the study. Employees with employability traits and a positive work environment result in employee productivity and high performance.

2.5 Theoretical Framework

The first independent variable is anchored on the theory of Becker (2009) Human Capital Theory, which states that employability is capable of self-improvement. And professional progress through investments in education, work experience, achievement, awareness of personal skills required for success in their chosen area, and productivity competency development. The second independent variable is anchored on the theory of Herzberg (1950), as cited by Fugar (2007), who stated that the work environment is a relevant factor that contributes to job satisfaction, achievement, responsibility, and advancement, including corporate strategy and governance, monitoring, remuneration, social communication, and workplace safety. The dependent variable is anchored on the theory of Taylor (1919) Scientific Management Theory, which states that employee productivity is the workers' knowledge of their job, and it is the starting point for improving employee productivity. It enabled given the intellectual capacity to do much higher, more interesting, finally more developing, and more productive work. Many businesses' performance determines by their workforce's ability to fulfill their tasks and the establishment's strategic goals. Taylor asserts employees will be more content if they make more production.

The first independent variable in the study is supported by Fugate and Kinicki (2008, p.512). Illustrates employability is a disposition that fosters individual characteristics that include openness to changes at work, work and career proactivity, career motivation, work and career resilience, optimism at work, and work identity.

The second independent variable in the study is supported by Pelfrene et al. (2001, p. 304). To address current work environment challenges for both employees and organizations include decision latitude (a combined scale of skill discretion and decision authority), psychological demands, supervisor social support, and co-worker social support.

While the dependent variable supported by Buuri (2015, p.15) said that employee productivity refers to workforce productivity that includes efficiency, quality, timeliness, and effectiveness, employees who participate in the evaluation, organizational objectives, or solution processes have higher employee productivity.

2.6 Conceptual Framework

Presented in Figure 1 is the Conceptual Framework of the study. As the framework shows, the first independent variable is employability (Fugate & Kinicki 2008). These indicators include openness to changes at work, work and career proactivity, career motivation, work and career resilience, and optimism at work and work identity. In this study, *openness to changes at work* means employees who are open to change are flexible and willing to adapt to new situations. Also, in this study, *work and career proactivity*, everyone's attitudes and behaviors in gathering knowledge that may affect their jobs and career choices, both within and outside their current employer, are reflected in proactive career orientation. *Career motivation* in this study describes a combination of human qualities and connected employment decisions and actions, consistent pursuit of a goal, and driven by obstacles. In this study, *work and career resilience* are linked to individual qualities, a sense of self, perseverance, and determination when challenged. In this study, *optimism at work* is generally happiness, considering the big picture, and striving for success. Lastly, the individual defines *work identity* in this study as they assume specific roles in the workplace.

The second independent variable is the work environment (Pelfrene et al. 2001) with the indicators of decision latitude, psychological demands, supervisor social support, and co-worker social support. *Decision latitude* in this study means how one can decide (skill discretion) and exercise control over their work (decision authority). *Psychological demands* exist in a work setting when individuals' interpersonal and social characteristics and positions are well aligned. In this study, *supervisor social support* is how leaders value their employees' contributions, fair treatment to the employees, and care about their well-being. *Co-worker social support* entails aiding one another in their responsibilities when necessary by sharing information and skills and providing guidance and support.

While the dependent variable of this study is employee productivity by Buuri (2015) with indicators of efficiency, quality, timeliness, and effectiveness, in this study, *efficiency* refers to a process feature that demonstrates

how the process achieves the desired output with the least amount of resources. *Quality* refers to how well a product or service has met the customer's needs and expectations in this study. In this study, employers used *timeliness* to determine whether employees completed a set of activities timely and accurate manner. And *effectiveness*, in this study, refers to a process characteristic showing how the process output conforms to requirements.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

2.7 Significance of the study

The results of this study are beneficial to particular groups of individuals and industries. First, to the banks of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro. This study will show which variable has more significant factors on employee productivity required for successful operational performance. Second, to the bank's employees in different offices and branches. This study will help them understand the nature of their work that will help them realize the importance of employability, work environment, and employee productivity in organizational effectiveness. When employees feel productive and may contribute to the organization's overall operation, they gain a sense of purpose. This purpose inspires them to strive to be their best.

Lastly, academic research contributes to both theoretical and practical knowledge. It would help the researchers do further studies on the same. The result will give them ideas on which factors predict the employee's productivity as a support program for improving the output of every industry. The result provided in this study will help employers develop their employees and look after their wellness.

III. METHOD

3.1 Research Design

This study is quantitative descriptive non-experimental research using correlational with regression analysis technique. The researcher used this method to describe the link between three factors that the researcher had found. It determines the direction and magnitude of such association if there is. Correlational research focuses on creating connections between two or more variables in the same population and evaluating the statistical relationship, with little or no effort to control extraneous variables. (Gravetter & Wallnau, 2004; Leedy & Ormrod, 2010; Schmitz, 2012). The quantitative data about the phenomenon was the focus of this descriptive survey. The quantitative part is a suitable schedule for collecting data planned for target respondents to answer the questions – data collection using surveys. The study aimed to determine bank employees' employability, work environment, and employee productivity.

3.2 Population and Sample

The respondents who participated in this study are bank employees of the Provinces of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro. The target population is Seven Hundred (700) employees comprising the branch managers, middle-level

officers (operation managers, bookkeepers, accounting clerks, and etc.), and frontline staff (tellers, customer service representatives, marketing representatives, loan officers, collectors, and etc.).

The study used a stratified random sampling procedure to select a sample representing the entire population. The researcher used Slovin's formula to obtain the sample size: $n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$. Where n is the sample size, N is the population size, and e is the level of precision, sometimes called sampling error which is the range in which the actual value of the population is estimated to be. That is always expressed in percentage points, for example, $\pm 5\%$. The study will use a sampling error (e) of $\pm 5\%$. Hence, the sample size will be $n = \frac{700}{1 + 700(0.05)^2} = 255$. Therefore, the final sample size is 255. A sampling ratio is established by dividing the sample size by the population size, that is, $\frac{255}{700} = 0.3643$. 36.43% of the employees are selected from each category from each stratum. Finally, the distribution of samples per category for branch managers is thirteen (13) samples, middle-level officers have sixty-two (62) samples, and frontline staff has one hundred eighty (180) samples.

3.3 Research Instrument

The researcher used an adapted and modified questionnaire for the independent and dependent variables according to the study's needs. The literature was used to help create the questionnaire, which will be validated by a panel of internal and external validators. Respondents will receive a questionnaire with demographic information on the employees and three sets of questionnaires for the independent and dependent variables.

The first independent variable is employability with indicators such as openness to changes at work, work and career proactivity, career motivation, work and career resilience, optimism at work, and work identity. The instrument used in this study was derived from a 2008 study by Fugate and Kinicki, entitled "A dispositional approach to employability: Development of a measure and test of implications for employee reactions to organizational change."

The second independent variable is the work environment with indicators such as decision latitude, psychological demands, supervisor social support, and co-worker social support. The instrument used in this variable is adapted from Pelfrene, Vlerick, Mak, De Smet, Kornitzer, and De Backer (2001), entitled "Scale reliability and validity of the Karasek 'Job Demand-Control-Support' model in the Belstress study."

The dependent variable of this study is the employee productivity of bank employees of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro with indicators such as efficiency, quality, timeliness, and effectiveness. The instrument used in this variable is adapted from Buuri (2015) study entitled "Performance Measurement Practices and Employee Productivity in the Insurance Firms in Kenya."

The original questionnaires are modified to contextualize the local banks' setting. The committee validated the questionnaire before the administration to the respondents and had undergone validation by external validators. It has also experienced the reliability test using Cronbach Alpha. The questionnaires were pilot-tested on cooperative banks, which were not part of the identified respondents of the study. The researcher used the five-point Likert Scale anchored at (5) Very High, (4) High, (3) Moderate, (2) Low, and (1) Very Low.

3.4 Data Collection

The researcher was able to do the following procedures in collecting relevant data for this research's productivity.

Firstly, the researcher sought the securing approval to conduct the study from the Graduate School program chairperson and their recommendation. A letter of consent is sought from the Managers of the participating banks of the provinces of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro as permission to conduct the study. Upon accepting the letter, the researcher sought a letter of endorsement to accommodate the researcher to administer the questionnaire to the identified respondents.

Further, before the survey questionnaire was handed out, the researcher sought the validation of questionnaires from competent internal and external evaluators. Then, the researcher's manuscript is reviewed by the UM Ethics Review Center. After which, it was pilot-tested for the assurance of its credibility. Next, the researcher explained the means and importance of questionnaires to the respondents. The tool used was electronic mail, Facebook messenger, text messaging, and face-to-face communication, provided that the researcher appropriately observed safety protocols during this time of the pandemic.

Then, a combination of personal distribution and technology approaches in the distribution of questionnaires in data gathering, retrieval, and dissemination of information. The researcher handed out the questionnaires in their office for those who could be reached. The researcher gave instructions and orientation to the respondents to guide them in going along with the questionnaires. After the respondents had answered all the items, the researcher retrieved the survey questionnaire. Also, after the questionnaires were recovered, it disinfected and remained in a box for seven (7) days.

For those who were unreachable because of the situation brought by COVID-19 and the respondents were having work-from-home and other alternative work arrangements. In this era of the “new normal,” online and offline approaches are safer in data gathering. The questionnaires are sent through electronic mail, Facebook messenger, or any technologies in the data gathering and collected later to give them enough time to answer the questions most accurately and explain the research tool and its purpose.

Finally, the researcher collated and totaled all the data collected from the respondents before doing a statistical analysis. The statistical information was evaluated and presented. With the information in hand, the researcher concluded and made recommendations based on the study's findings.

3.5 Statistical Tools

The statistical tools used for data analysis and interpretations are:

Mean. This was used to determine the level of employability, work environment, and employee productivity of bank employees.

Pearson-r. This was used to determine the significant relationship between employability to employee productivity and work environment to employee productivity of banks employees.

Multiple Regression Analysis. This was used to determine what domain significantly best predicts employability and work environment to employee productivity of banks employees in the provinces of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro.

IV. RESULTS

The data obtained from the respondents on Employability and Work Environment as Predictors to Employee Productivity the presented, evaluated, and constructed in this section based on the research objectives. The orders of discussion on the mentioned topic are as follows: level of employability, level of work environment, level of employee productivity, the significance of the relationship of employability and work environment to employee productivity, regression analysis on the influence of employability and work environment to employee productivity, regression analysis on the influence of the domains of employability to employee productivity, and regression analysis on the influence of the domains of the work environment to employee productivity.

The standard deviation is used to determine the error on unknown samples. The researcher cannot note that the standard deviation ranges from 0.58 to 0.71, which is lesser than 1.0 as the typical standard deviation for the 5-points Likert scale (Wittink& Bayer, 1994). That means the accomplished questionnaires' ratings are close to the mean, indicating the consistency of responses among the respondents.

4.1 Level of Employability

Table shows the level of employability of the bank's employees of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro, with an overall mean of 4.33 and a standard deviation of 0.46, as described as very high. The result implied that employees very much observed the level of employability. That means that the respondents are very much observed employability in *openness to changes at work, work and career proactivity, career motivation, work and career resilience, optimism at work, and work identity*. The cited total mean score was the outcome acquired from the subsequent computed mean scores from the highest to lowest indicators: 4.46 or very high for *optimism at work*; 4.39 or very high for *openness to changes at work*; 4.37 or very high for *career motivation*; 4.31 or high for *work identity*; 4.29 or high for *work and career proactivity*; and 4.14 or high for *work and career resilience*.

Table 1. *Level of Employability*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Openness to Changes at Work	4.39	0.57	Very High
Work and Career Proactivity	4.29	0.59	Very High
Career Motivation	4.37	0.54	Very High
Work and Career Resilience	4.14	0.63	High
Optimism at Wok	4.46	0.53	Very High
Work Identity	4.31	0.59	Very High
Overall	4.33	0.46	Very High

4.2 Level of Work Environment

Employability and Work Environment as Predictors to Employee Productivity of Banks Employees

As shown in Table 2, the overall mean score results of the work environment responded by the bank's employees is 4.19 with a standard deviation of 0.47. It reflects a high descriptive level regarding the work environment level, which implies that it is much observed. That means that the respondents are much observed the work environment in the items of *decision latitude*, *psychological demands*, *supervisor social support*, and *co-worker social support*. The cited total mean score was the outcome acquired from the subsequent computed mean scores from the highest to lowest indicators: 4.43 or very high for the *supervisor social support*; 4.20 or very high for the *co-worker social support*; 4.08 or high for the *decision latitude*; and 4.07 or high for the *psychological demands*.

Table 2. Level of Work Environment

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Decision Latitude	4.08	0.56	High
Psychological Demands	4.07	0.62	High
Supervisor and social support	4.43	0.61	Very High
Co-worker social support	4.20	0.77	Very High
Overall	4.19	0.47	High

4.3 Level of Employee Productivity

As shown in Table 3, the overall mean score results of employee productivity responded by the banks' employees of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro is 4.31, with a standard deviation of 0.48, which is very high. The result implied that the employees very much observe the level of employee productivity in the items of *efficiency*, *quality*, *timeliness*, and *effectiveness*. The cited total mean score was the outcome acquired from the subsequent computed mean scores from the highest to lowest indicators: 4.36 or very high for *timeliness*; 4.33 or very high for *effectiveness*; 4.31 or very high for *quality*; and, 4.23 or very high for *efficiency*.

Table 3. Level of Employee Productivity

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Efficiency	4.23	0.60	Very High
Quality	4.31	0.55	Very High
Timeliness	4.36	0.54	Very High
Effectiveness	4.33	0.54	Very High
Overall	4.31	0.48	Very High

4.4 Significance of the Relationship of Employability and Work Environment to Employee Productivity

The correlation between employability and work environment to employee productivity of the bank's employees is presented in Table 4. The computation using Person-r revealed that employability got an r-value of 0.729 with an r-square of 0.5314 and p-value of 0.001. The work environment gets an r-value of 0.718, with an r-square of 0.5155, and a p-value of 0.001; hence, there is a significant relationship between employability and work environment to employee productivity.

Furthermore, as presented in the table, the hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between employability and work environment and employee productivity of banks employees of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro, is rejected.

Table 4. Significance of the Relationship of Employability and Work Environment to Employee Productivity

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable	r-value	r-square	p-value	Decision
Employability	Employee Productivity	0.729	0.5314	0.001	H ₀ is rejected

Work Environment	0.718	0.5155	0.001	H ₀ is rejected
------------------	-------	--------	-------	----------------------------

*p<0.05

4.5 Regression Analysis on the Influence of Employability and Work Environment to Employee Productivity

Presented in Table 5 is a regression analysis of the influence of employability and work environment on employee productivity. The table shows a computed F-ratio of 187.976 and a P-value of 0.001, which means a significant effect of employability and work environment on employee productivity. The R-value of 0.744* indicates a positive relationship between employability and work environment to employee productivity. The overall R² is 0.599, meaning that 59.9% of the employability and work environment level, and the remaining percentage is accountable to the other indicators not included in the study.

Table 5. Regression Analysis on the Influence of Employability and Work Environment to Employee Productivity

Independent Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	SE				
(constant)	0.693	0.188				
Employability	0.454	0.063	0.436*	7.233	0.001	H ₀ is rejected
Work Environment	0.393	0.061	0.391*	6.489	0.001	H ₀ is rejected
Dependent Variable:			Employee Productivity			
R = 0.744*			R ² = 0.599			
F-ratio = 187.976			P-value = 0.001			

4.6 Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Domains of Employability to Employee Productivity

Presented in Table 6 is the regression analysis on the influence of the domains of employability on employee productivity. The table shows computed F-ratio of 50.543 and a P-value of 0.001, so there is a significant influence of the domains of employability on employee productivity. The R-value of 0.742* showed a positive relationship between employability to employee productivity. The overall R² is 0.550, indicating that 55.0% of the level of employability comprises openness to changes at work, work and career proactivity, career motivation, work and career resilience, optimism at work, and work identity. And the remaining percentage is accountable to the other indicators not included in the study.

Table 6. Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Domains of Employability to Employee Productivity

Independent Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	SE				
(constant)	0.956	0.198				
Openness to Changes at Work	0.140	0.048	0.169*	2.908	0.004	H ₀ is rejected
Work and Career Proactivity	0.108	0.054	0.135*	2.002	0.046	H ₀ is rejected
Career Motivation	0.269	0.057	0.306*	4.753	0.001	H ₀ is rejected
Work and Career Resilience	0.062	0.043	0.082	1.430	0.154	H ₀ is not rejected

Optimism at Work	0.096	0.058	0.107	1.663	0.098	H ₀ is not rejected
Work Identity	0.097	0.049	0.120	1.961	0.051	H ₀ is not rejected
Dependent Variable:		Employee Productivity				
R = 0.742*		R ² = 0.550				
F-ratio = 50.543		P-value = 0.001				

Moreover, openness to changes at work has a beta of 0.169* with a p-value of 0.004; work and career proactivity have a beta of 0.135* with a p-value of 0.046; career motivation has a beta of 0.306 with a p-value of 0.001; work and career resilience have a beta of 0.082 with a p-value of 0.154; optimism at work has a beta of 0.107 with a p-value of 0.098, and work identity has a beta of 0.120 with a p-value of 0.051. Indicators of openness to changes at work, work and career proactivity, and career motivation significantly influence Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro banks employees' prediction of employee productivity. Work and career resilience, optimism at work and work identity do not significantly influence employee productivity.

Therefore, as presented in the table, the first hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between employability and employee productivity of banks employees of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro is rejected on indicators: openness to changes at work, work and career proactivity and career motivation. While career resilience, optimism at work, and work identity are the null hypothesis is not rejected.

4.7 Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Domains of Work Environment to Employee Productivity

Presented in Table 7 is the regression analysis on the influence of the domains of work environment on employee productivity. The table showed a computed F-ratio of 74.632 and a P-value of 0.001, which means there is a significant influence on the domains of the work environment on employee productivity. The R-value of 0.738* indicated a positive relationship between work environment to employee productivity. The overall R² is 0.544, showing that 54.4% of the work environment level is explained by decision latitude, psychological demands, supervisor social support, and co-worker social support. Other indicators not included in the study are responsible for the remaining percentage.

Moreover, decision latitude has a beta of 0.373* with a p-value of 0.001; psychological demands have a beta of 0.196* with a p-value of 0.001; supervisor social support has a beta of 0.255 with a p-value of 0.001, and co-worker social support has a beta of 0.152 with a p-value of 0.002. All indicators of the dependent variable have a corresponding 0.001 and 0.002 p-value, which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, decision latitude, psychological demands, supervisor social support, and co-worker social support significantly influence Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro employees' prediction of employee productivity.

Therefore, as presented in the table, the second hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between work environment and employee productivity of banks employees of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro is rejected on all indicators: decision latitude, psychological demands, supervisor social support, and co-worker social support.

Table 7. *Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Domains of Work Environment to Employee Productivity*

Independent Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	SE				
(constant)	1.127	0.187				
Decision Latitude	0.316	0.044	0.373*	7.174	0.001	H ₀ is rejected
Psychological Demands	0.150	0.038	0.196*	3.911	0.001	H ₀ is rejected
Supervisor social support	0.199	0.039	0.255*	5.115	0.001	H ₀ is rejected
Co-worker social support	0.094	0.030	0.152*	3.087	0.002	H ₀ is rejected
Dependent Variable:		Employee Productivity				
R = 0.738*		R ² = 0.544				
F-ratio = 74.632		P-value = 0.001				

V. DISCUSSION

The data on employability, work environment, and employee productivity of bank employees are presented in this chapter, and the said discussion is based on the results that appeared in the previous section.

5.1 Level of Employability

In the previous chapter, the researcher found that the level of employability in the banks' employees of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro was very high. That entails that most respondents decided in terms of openness to changes at work, work and career proactivity, career motivation, optimism at work, and work identity are very much observed by the employees. And the employees much observe work and career resilience. The very high level of employability of employees is because of the increased rating given by the respondents in each indicator. That further implied that the employees could strive for success, be receptive and willing to change, and be persistent toward a purpose. Motivated by challenges, assume specific roles, have high self-evaluations, and be confident and persistent when challenged.

More so, results show that the *optimism at work* was very high. It is the most significant element in establishing employability in the organization. That was aligned with the study of Jabbar et al. (2019), who said employees with a positive attitude toward their careers are more employable and productive.

Moreover, employability in terms of *openness to changes at work* was also very high; that means that the employees who are open to change are receptive and adaptable. Researchers related in the study conducted by Augustsson et al. (2017) that individuals who are available to new experiences and changes can better adjust to demanding job and career conditions, which increases their employability.

In addition, employability in terms of *career motivation* was also very high, which means employees are objective, dedicated to a mission, and driven by a sense of accomplishment. It was the same in Cheng et al. (2015); highly motivated individuals about their jobs will gain new abilities and see unexpected situations as opportunities and essential elements of employability.

Additionally, employability in terms of *work identity* was also very high. Results implied the work identity has a significant positive impact on the employees having a positive sense of commitment and position alignment. That is similar to the study of Fabio (2017), who said that work identity improves employability by providing motivation, direction, and a sense of purpose to job-related activities.

Also, employability in terms of *work and career proactivity* was very high. That means that employees achieve something great at work and can contribute ideas that would benefit the organization. As stated, and parallel to the study of Wang and Parker (2015), career proactivity in the workplace and one's profession entails consciously controlling oneself and one's environment to make things happen. It comprises longing for and working for progressive change to achieve a better and more desirable future.

Subsequently, employability in terms of *work and career resilience* is high, which means employees are optimistic about future career opportunities. This finding is congruent with Aurora and Rangnekar (2016), who said that employees with positive self-evaluation lead to constructive behaviors, and optimism encourages positive future goals. As a result, people's faith in their capacity to deal with the goals and emotional challenges of their occupations and discover and realize career opportunities or employability in difficult situations increases.

5.2 Level of Work Environment

The previous chapter also revealed that the employees' work environment in the banks of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro was high. That implied that the employees much observed the work environment. The high level of employees' work environment is because of the high rating given by the respondents on each indicator. This further implies that the employees could take control of their work. There is a good fit between employees' interpersonal and emotional competencies. The leaders value their employees' contribution and care about their wellbeing, assisting one another in their tasks and providing encouragement and support.

The work environment in terms of *supervisor social support* was very high, which means employees get close attention from their supervisor and are highly concerned about the welfare of the employees. In congruence, Collins et al. (2016) study said that leaders who value their employees' accomplishments and care about their wellbeing provide supervisor social support. These benefits could increase job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and job performance

At the same time, *co-worker social support* was very high, which implies that people helped each other with their tasks when they needed it by sharing their knowledge, skills, and support. Similarly, Raziqa and Maulabakhsh (2015) literature said that co-worker social support boosts workplace happiness and performance by reducing employee stress. Social support from co-workers is critical in the work environment for maintaining productive working relationships.

As part of this, the work environment in terms of *decision latitude* was high, which means employees could develop their abilities and have the power to adopt or reject an innovation by someone in a position. As Ajala (2017)

study stated, who said decision latitude is the employee's ability to choose how to meet the demands. Similarly, the literature by Crescenzo (2016) said that is the degree to which the job needs a diversity of activities and an opportunity to learn new skills. Also the employees' ability to decide about and control their positions. The researcher has communicated to firms, particularly financial institutions, that improving decision latitude means increasing and maintaining employee productivity.

Furthermore, the work environment in terms of *psychological demands* was high, which means employees required enough time to get the job done. As comparable to the study by Kersemaekers et al. (2018), psychological demands exist in a work environment where employees' interpersonal and emotional competencies are well-matched to the job's needs. As a result, psychological demands affected workers' mental health. As a result, businesses must devise methods to encourage employees to put up their best efforts to attain the highest production level.

5.3 Level of Employee Productivity

The level of employee productivity as per results from the preceding chapter shows a very high level of productivity. That means that employees very much observed the employee productivity in the banks in the efficiency, quality, timeliness, and effectiveness. The very high level of employee productivity is because respondents gave it a good rating. That further implies that the employees could produce the required output at minimum resource cost, meet customer requirements and expectations, work correctly and on time, and process output conforms to requirements.

Employee productivity in terms of *timeliness* was very high. That means employees produced and delivered on time or within the set deadlines of their work. Parallel to Mutuku and Nyaribo (2015) study, employee productivity is how much time an employee spends producing the required results. The timeliness factor determines if it finished a piece of work correctly and is on time. As a result, timeliness is critical to keeping consumers happy, fostering long-term loyalty, and motivating staff to do their best work. All of which help boost your company's market position.

Seemingly, the employee productivity in terms of *effectiveness* was also very high. That means an employee's efficacy measures regularly to ensure that the goal of generating high-quality work all the time. The same study conducted by Okeke et al. (2016) revealed that effectiveness considers the quality of our outcomes and the degree. A successful worker works to accomplish assignments as quickly as possible, solve difficulties creatively, and continuously improve productivity.

Employee productivity in terms of *quality* was very high. That means a product or service meets or surpasses a client's criteria, customer satisfaction, and expectations of the bank employees. That is also related to the study of Salimi (2015) suggested that employees must generate valuable work of high quality. It is high quality if the consumers are satisfied. As a result, employee productivity is measured not just in terms of quantity but also in terms of the quality of output.

Indeed, the employee productivity in terms of *efficiency* was also very high. That shows that they stick to deadlines and don't spend too much time on a single project. Consonance to Hanaysha (2016) said that employee productivity measures a worker's or a group of workers' efficiencies. They make good use of their working hours to produce more and better results in less time. They do a good job and finish a lot of things. The effectiveness of an organization's staff is critical to its success, and it is an essential factor to consider.

5.4 Significance of the Relationship of Employability and Work Environment to Employee Productivity

The test of the relationship between three variables involved in the study proves a significant relationship between employability and work environment to employee productivity, implying that there is a direct correlation between the employability and work environment that the employee has and the employee productivity of the organization.

This is supported by the study by Yorke (2019) that the employer's primary aim is to hire highly employable individuals. Since they are top achievers, employability may help a company achieve exceptional performance, sustainable competitiveness, and profitability. Hence, employability and employee productivity are linked at an individual and organizational level. It also related this to the proposition of McCowan (2015), who said that employability is a series of experiences that make a person a high-performing individual. Therefore, positively related employability to employee productivity in the organization and society.

Sumiyati et al. (2016) also stated that companies have a pleasant work environment and continually support their staff significantly correlates to increased employee happiness, motivation, teamwork, and productivity. The study conducted by Al-Omari (2017) stated that improving the work environment motivates the employees, achieves the job's desired outcomes and objectives and increases employee productivity.

5.5 Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Domains of Employability to Employee Productivity

The regression analysis on the influence of the domains of employability to employee productivity showed that the domains such as openness to changes at work, work and career proactivity, and career motivation significantly influence Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro banks employees' prediction of employee productivity. Work and career resilience, optimism at work, and work identity do not significantly influence employee productivity.

The results showed that *openness to changes* at work significantly influences employee productivity. That is in line with Yue and Ferguson (2019), who claimed that openness to change at work includes personal traits and leadership. Transparent internal communication also boosts employee productivity throughout times of change, resulting in increased willingness to change. Developing an openness to changes at work depends on how an individual attribute develops and how organizational leadership interacts with communication elements to impact change results.

Moreover, the results revealed that *work and career proactivity* significantly influence employee productivity. That is parallel to the study conducted by Wang, Thomas, Yu, and Spitzmueller (2017), which stated that work and career proactivity is the ability to act, take on responsibility, and plan, decision-making to achieve a previously established goal. Thus, employees with proactive personalities are more productive and successful in their careers.

Further, the result presented that *career motivation* significantly influences employee productivity because of a willingness to work hard to achieve one's career objectives. That is congruent with Baethge, Rigotti, and Hoeper (2017) study, which argued that career motivation refers to the desire to put forth an effort to attain one's job goals. It also comes with advanced features of needs, interests, and personal attributes representing the stimulation, direction, and persistence of working life behaviors. Employees with high career motivation demonstrated a solid responsibility for work-related goals and a desire for professional growth and increased productivity.

In another way, work and *career resilience* have no significant influence the employee productivity. That means there is no significant correlation between work and career resilience and employee productivity. That is an anchored study by Ojo, Fawehinmi, and Yusliza (2021) that career resilience is insufficient for such individuals to control their work during disruptive times. However, management could stimulate their employees' resilience by providing them with training programs that give them the ability and tactics to deal with future challenges.

Obtaining *optimism at work* has no significant influence on employee productivity. That means there is no significant correlation between optimism at work and employee productivity. That is in line with Ugwu and Igbende (2017), who claimed that optimism at work is not enough for healthier, more engaged leadership, and hard work. No framework exists to help conceptualize the relationship between optimism at work and employee productivity.

Lastly, *work identity* has no significant influence on employee productivity. That means there is no significant correlation between work identity and employee productivity. It resembled the study presented by Bryan and Nandi (2018), which argued that work identity is a so-called traditional work or occupational identity. It means people become employed by a company to work for that company in a particular position to enact their career and occupational activities. No framework exists to help conceptualize the relationship between work identity and employee productivity.

5.6 Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Domains of Work Environment to Employee Productivity

The regression analysis on the influence of the domains of the work environment to employee productivity showed that the domains such as decision latitude, psychological demands, supervisor social support, and co-worker social support significantly influence Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro banks employees' prediction of employee productivity.

The result showed that *decision latitude* significantly influences employee productivity. That is in line with Ziae, Choobineh, Eramaki, Ghaem, and Jaber (2019), who claimed that the control over talent and time allocation and organizational decisions are two components of decision latitude. As a result, employees with a lot of decision-making power acquire a professional and personal interest in the organization, giving them the ability to influence the outcome of their work, resulting in higher employee productivity, a happy attitude, and overall success.

Additionally, the result presented that *psychological demands* significantly influence employee productivity. Just as the study conducted by Wanjira and Njiru (2020) stated that psychological demands comprise physical, social, or organizational requirements for physical and mental effort to be sustained, it must do with how the mind works and how it works thoughts and feelings affect behavior. Reducing job stress and enhanced employee wellbeing may lead to increased dedication to the organization, increasing employee productivity and career longevity.

Furthermore, the result presented that *supervisor social support* significantly influences employee productivity. That is congruent with the study of Burhanudin, Tjahjono, and Hartono (2020); they claimed that supervisor social support focuses on assisting employees in achieving personal success at work and balancing work and family obligations. Employee work happiness, staff development, supervisor aids on-the-job learning, organizational commitment, and employee productivity social assistance.

Lastly, *co-worker social support* significantly influences employee productivity. That aligns with the study presented by Bateman (2019), which affirmed that co-worker social support assists other co-workers in their tasks to lighten workloads by sharing knowledge or expertise and providing encouragement and support, and caring about their wellbeing. Thus, employees communicate ideas more openly and honestly and help one another improve employee productivity and job satisfaction.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn the level of employability is very high for openness to changes at work, work and career proactivity, career motivation, optimism at work, work identity and high work and career resilience, and the overall mean of a very high for employability. The work environment level is very high for supervisor social support and co-worker social support and a high for decision latitude and psychological demands, and the overall mean of high for the work environment. Also, the level of employee productivity is very high with indicators of efficiency, quality, timeliness, and effectiveness, and the overall mean of a very high the level of employee productivity.

Furthermore, the study finds out that there is a significant relationship of employability and work environment to employee productivity. The combined employability and work environment indicators influence employee productivity; thus, employability and work environment predict employee productivity. Therefore, the findings of this study confirm the anchored proposition of McCowan (2015), which stated that attributes of employability could enhance employee productivity in the workplace and provide benefits for the organization and society. As well as, the work environment has a significant influence to employee productivity. That is associated with Al-Omari and Okasheh (2017) concept that employers should improve the work environment so that employees will be motivated. The work environment substantially affects employees' well-being and develops interaction, collaboration, innovation, and employee productivity.

VII. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the preceding findings and conclusions, the researcher offers the following recommendations.

Employability is very high, including its indicators: openness to changes at work, work and career proactivity, career motivation, optimism at work, and work identity. Furthermore, work and career resilience were the lowest among the itemized responses. *"I am willing to make sacrifices in my personal life to achieve career success"*. The researcher recommends to the employees be engaged and flexible, schedule time to work and personal life, and set priorities to achieve their goals. Make personal life a priority without getting behind at work so you can build a good life, personal growth, and career success.

Conversely, the study finds a very high work environment result with indicators such as supervisor social support and co-worker social support and a high impact on decision latitude and psychological demands. The employee worked in a pleasant setting with low distractions, a high level of appropriate attention, compassion, and overall understanding between co-workers and supervisor. Regarding these results, the researcher recommends that the institution should strengthen to develop its work environment programs such as team-building activities, promoting wellness programs, healthy work-life balance, etc. Moreover, decision latitude is recognized as the lowest indicator, and the researcher recommends that the institution allows empowering and motivates employees to produce greater quantity and quality of work. That would positively contribute to the increasing level of the work environment.

Likewise, the above study emphasizes the importance of employee productivity and various aspects, like employability and work environment, that significantly affect it. The outcome of this study finds a very high level of employee productivity, although item number 1 was identified as the lowest item that focuses on efficiency. Based on the results, the researcher recommends managers may determine the employee's strengths and weaknesses to improve employee productivity. Managers might implement regular stand-up meetings in person or digitally, minimize busy work, give constructive feedback and give praise or reward during monthly meetings or any institutional activities to appreciate their efforts and keep your employees motivated.

Furthermore, the significant relationship between employability and work environment on employee productivity implies that employability and work environment conceivably may affect the level of employee productivity. With that, the employability and work environment of the institution depends on the employee productivity in place. Hence, the employability and work environment in the area are the only factors that can affect an organization's employee productivity. Future researchers may use another evaluation tool with different indicators for further studies as it may have a different result and implication.

According to the findings of this research, there was a domain in employability and work environment that significantly affects employee productivity. Thus, further researchers recommend that independent and dependent

variables have various parameters and dimensions; and different indicators that could affect employee productivity may be conducted.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ajala, E., 2017. The influence of workplace environment on workers' welfare, performance and productivity. The African Symposium 12(1): 141-149. Available at: http://ir.library.ui.edu.ng/bitstream/123456789/2952/1/%2821%29ui_art_ajala_influence_2012.pdf
- [2] Al-Omari, K. and Okasheh, H., 2017. The influence of work environment on job performance: A case study of engineering company in Jordan. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, 12(24), pp.15544-15550. Available at: https://www.ripublication.com/ijaer17/ijaerv12n24_223.pdf
- [3] Arora, R. and Rangnekar, S., 2016. Moderating mentoring relationships and career resilience: Role of conscientiousness personality disposition. *Journal of Workplace Behavioral Health*, 31(1), pp.19-36. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ridhi-Arora-3/publication/290392172_Moderating_mentoring_relationships_and_career_resilience_Role_of_conscientiousness_personality_disposition/links/569f879608ae2c638eb7aa71/Moderating-mentoring-relationships-and-career-resilience-Role-of-conscientiousness-personality-disposition.pdf
- [4] Augustsson, H., Richter, A., Hasson, H. and von Thiele Schwarz, U., 2017. The need for dual openness to change: a longitudinal study evaluating the impact of employees' openness to organizational change content and process on intervention outcomes. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 53(3), pp.349-368.
- [5] Awan, A.G. and Tahir, M.T., 2015. Impact of working environment on employee's productivity: A case study of Banks and Insurance Companies in Pakistan. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(1), pp.329-345. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/download/49979273/1_literature_yasin_sheikh.pdf
- [6] Baci, L.E., Dinca, M., Lazar, T. and Sandvin, J.T., 2016. Exploring the social relations of Roma employability: The case of rural segregated communities in Romania. *Journal of Comparative Social Work*, 11(1).
- [7] Baethge, A., Rigotti, T. and Vincent-Hoeper, S., 2017. How followers differing in career motivation gain career profits from transformational leaders: A longitudinal moderated mediation model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, p.1527. Available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01527/full>
- [8] Baily, M.N., Farrell, D., Greenberg, E., Henrich, J.D., Jinjo, N., Jolles, M. and Remes, J., 2015. Increasing global competition and labor productivity: Lessons from the US automotive industry. *McKensie Global Institute*, November, 7. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Martin-Baily/publication/5034066_Increasing_global_competition_and_labor_productivity_lessons_from_the_US_automotive_industry/links/00b49519d0d1e03c13000000/Increasing-global-competition-and-labor-productivity-lessons-from-the-US-automotive-industry.pdf
- [9] Bateman, G., 2019. Employee perceptions of co-worker support and its effect on job satisfaction, work stress and intention to quit. Available at: http://ir.canterbury.ac.nz/bitstream/handle/10092/4050/Thesis_fulltext.pdf
- [10] Becker, G.S., 2009. *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education*. University of Chicago press. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/download/58822050/BECKER_HumanCapital_Cp1_3.pdf
- [11] Bryan, M. and Nandi, A., 2015. *Working hours, work identity and subjective wellbeing* (No. 2015-21). Retrieved Available at: ISER Working Paper Series. <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/163526/1/848631587.pdf>
- [12] Burhanudin, B., Tjahjono, H., Eq, Z. and Hartono, A., 2020. Work-family enrichment as a mediator effect of supervisor support, self-esteem, and optimism on job satisfaction. *Management Science Letters*, 10(10), pp.2269-2280. Available at: http://m.growingscience.com/msl/Vol10/msl_2020_59.pdf
- [13] Buuri, D.W., 2015. *Performance measurement practices and employee productivity in the insurance firms in Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi). Available at: http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/11295/94455/Buuri_Performance%20measurement%20practices.pdf?sequence=1
- [14] Career Guide, 2020. Positive Working Environment: Definition and Characteristics. Available at: <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/positive-working-environment>
- [15] Cheng, M., Cheng, C., Tian, Y. and Fan, X., 2015. Student nurses' motivation to choose gerontological nursing as a career in China: A survey study. *Nurse Education Today*, 35(7), pp.843-848. Retrieved November 13, 2020, from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2015.03.001>.

- [16] Collins, A.M., Hislop, D. and Cartwright, S., 2016. Social support in the workplace between teleworkers, office-based colleagues and supervisors. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 31(2), pp.161-175. Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/ntwe.12065>
- [17] Crescenzo, P., 2016. An ancient theory for a current problem [Review of the book *Healthy Work: Stress, productivity and the reconstruction of working life*, by RA Karasek& T. Theorell]. *Journal of Health and Social Sciences*, 1(3), pp.287-292. Available at: <https://journalhss.com/wp-content/uploads/JHHS13.pdf#page=131>
- [18] Fabio, A.D., 2017. A review of empirical studies on employability and measures of employability. *Psychology of career adaptability, employability and resilience*, pp.107-123. Available at: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-66954-0_7
- [19] Fugar, F.D., 2007. Frederick Herzberg's motivation-hygiene theory revisited: The concept and its applicability to clergy (A study of fulltime stipendiary clergy of the global evangelical church, Ghana. *Journal of Science and Technology (Ghana)*, 27(1), pp.119-130. Available at: <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/just/article/download/33031/63451>
- [20] Fugate, M. and Kinicki, A.J., 2008. A dispositional approach to employability: Development of a measure and test of implications for employee reactions to organizational change. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 81(3), pp.503-527. Available at: from <https://scholar.google.com/scholar>
- [21] Gravetter, F.J. and Wallnau, L.B., 2004. *Statistics for the behavioral sciences*. Belmont, CA: Thompson-Wadsworth. Hopkins, TM (2004). *Gender issues in mathematics achievement in Tennessee: Does rural school locale matter*.
- [22] Hanaysha, J., 2016. Improving employee productivity through work engagement: Evidence from higher education sector. *Management Science Letters*, 6(1), pp.61-70. Available at: http://m.growingscience.com/msl/Vol6/msl_2015_114.pdf
- [23] Hanaysha, J., 2016. Testing the effects of employee empowerment, teamwork, and employee training on employee productivity in higher education sector. *International Journal of Learning and Development*, 6(1), pp.164-178. Available at: https://scholar.google.com/Jalal_Hanaysha/publication/301884662.pdf
- [24] Harness, J., 2018, The Importance of Productivity. Available at: <https://bizfluent.com/info-8292773-importance-employee-productivity.html>
- [25] Herbert, B., 2016. Moving employee talent key to competitive edge. *Strategic HR Review*.
- [26] Ibrahim, Y.A., 2021. *The Perceptions of Bank Employees on Performance Target* (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University). Available at: <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=12262&context=dissertations>
- [27] Jabbar, M.N., Nawaz, M., Rehman, F.U., Bhatti, G.A. and Choudhary, A., 2019. Does optimism and work engagement matter to improve job performance? An empirical study. *International Journal of Information, Business and Management*, 11(4), pp.170-176. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Muhammad-Jabbar>
- [28] Kersemaekers, W., Rupperecht, S., Wittmann, M., Tamdjidi, C., Falke, P., Donders, R., Speckens, A. and Kohls, N., 2018. A workplace mindfulness intervention may be associated with improved psychological well-being and productivity. A preliminary field study in a company setting. *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, p.195. Available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00195/full?sour>
- [29] Longenecker, C.O. and Fink, L.S., 2001. Improving management performance in rapidly changing organizations. *Journal of management development*.
- [30] McCowan, T., 2015. Should universities promote employability.? *Theory and Research in Education*, 13(3), pp.267-285. Available at: <https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/1498957/1/Should%20universities%20promote%20employability,%20aut hor%20draft.pdf>
- [31] Mutuku, M.N. and Nyaribo, W.M., 2015. Effect of information technology on employee productivity in selected banks in Kenya. *Review of Contemporary Business Research*, 4(1), pp.49-57. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Nyaribo-Misuko-2/publication/282840537>
- [32] Nepangue-Seaman, R, Saban, GA, Balila, J, Rodriguez, J and Barrios, R., 2016 *Employability and Employee Productivity as Mediated by Core Competencies of Nurse Educators: Basis for Human Resource Training and Retention Program*. Adventist University of the Philippines, p.7.
- [33] Ojo, A.O., Fawehinmi, O. and Yusliza, M.Y., 2021. Examining the Predictors of Resilience and Work Engagement during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 2902. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/5/2902/pdf>
- [34] Okeke, M.N., Echo, O. and Oboreh, J.C., 2016. Effects of stress on employee productivity. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 42(3495), pp.1-12. Available at: http://www.arabianjbmr.com/pdfs/AC_VOL_2_11/2.pdf

- [35] Onyije, O.C., 2015. Effect of performance appraisal on employee productivity in a Nigerian University. *Journal of economics and business research*, 21(2), pp.65-81. Available at: <http://www.uav.ro/jour/index.php/jebr/article/download/518/pdf>.
- [36] Pelfrene, E., Vlerick, P., Mak, R.P., De Smet, P., Kornitzer, M. and De Backer, G., 2001. Scale reliability and validity of the Karasek'Job Demand-Control-Support' model in the Belstress study. *Work & stress*, 15(4), pp.297-313. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Peter_Vlerick/publication/2630428
- [37] Raziq, A. and Maulabakhsh, R., 2015. Impact of working environment on job satisfaction. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 23, pp.717-725. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212567115005249>
- [38] Saatchi, M., 2017, "Productivity psychology", Tehran, Virayesh Publication. (In Persian).
- [39] Salimi, M., 2015, "Role of Human Resource Productivity and Knowledge Management". *Labor and Society*, No.88, pp.49-63.
- [40] Sitohong, N., 2020. Effect of work environment to employee performance in PT Abadi Motor Indonesia. Vol.8 (Iss.2).
- [41] Sumiyati, M., Purnama, R. and Pratama, K.F., 2016. The influence of social work environment on employee productivity in manufacturing in Indonesia. *Atlantis Press*, 15, pp.649-652. Available at: <https://www.atlantispress.com/article/25865996.pdf>
- [42] Taylor, F.W., 1919. *The principles of scientific management*. Harper & brothers. Available at: <https://dspace.gipe.ac.in/xmlui/bitstream/handle/10973/41111/GIPE-191173.pdf?sequence=3>
- [43] Tien, H.L.S. and Wang, Y.C., 2017. Career adaptability, employability, and career resilience of Asian people. In *Psychology of career adaptability, employability and resilience* (pp. 299-314). Springer, Cham. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Hsiu-Lan-Shelley-Tien/publication/321535323_Career_Adaptability_Employability_and_Career_Resilience_of_Asian_People/links/5a5321eaaca2725638c7ea9f/Career-Adaptability-Employability-and-Career-Resilience-of-Asian-People.pdf
- [44] Ugwu, F.O. and Igbende, D.A., 2017. Going beyond borders: Work centrality, emotional intelligence and employee optimism as predictors of organizational citizenship behavior. *Cogent Psychology*, 4(1), p.1362805. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311908.2017.1362805>.
- [45] Vargas-Hernández, J.G. and Jiménez, R.A., 2016. Personal Marketing Plan and Its Influence on Employability. *RESPONSIBLE MARKETING FOR SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS*, p.63. Available at: [https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=Z5PnCwAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA63&dq=Personal+marketing+plan+and+its+influence+on+employability:+The+case+of+Engineers+in+business+management+graduate+of+ITLAC++Turkish+Economic+Review,+2\(2\),+1-7.&ots=XLhrcjiluf&sig=K4sRMmpPFcj6qqyBRz_05iESS3U](https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=Z5PnCwAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA63&dq=Personal+marketing+plan+and+its+influence+on+employability:+The+case+of+Engineers+in+business+management+graduate+of+ITLAC++Turkish+Economic+Review,+2(2),+1-7.&ots=XLhrcjiluf&sig=K4sRMmpPFcj6qqyBRz_05iESS3U)
- [46] Wang, L. and Parker, S., 2015. Helping people to make things happen: A framework for proactivity at work. *International Coaching Psychology Review*, 10(1). Available at: https://www.academia.edu/download/38714736/Parker_and_Wang_coaching_2015.pdf
- [47] Wang, Z., Zhang, J., Thomas, C.L., Yu, J. and Spitzmueller, C., 2017. Explaining benefits of employee proactive personality: The role of engagement, team proactivity composition and perceived organizational support. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 101, pp.90-103. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/download/63845942/Explaining_benefits_of_employee_proactive_personality_120200706-111020-1iygxqg.pdf
- [48] Wanjira, M.R. and Njiru, L., 2020. Influence of Psychological Demands on Job Satisfaction among the Employees of the National Hospital Insurance Fund in Kenya. *Editon Consortium Journal of Psychology, Guidance, and Counseling*, 2(1), pp.149-158. Available at: <https://editonpublishing.org/ecpj/index.php/ECJPGC/article/download/141/101>
- [49] Yorke, M., 2019. Employability in higher education: what it is – what it is not, HE Academy/ESECT, learning & employability series. Available at: <chromeextension://ohfgljdgelakfkefopgklcohadegdpjf/file>.
- [50] Yue, C.A., Men, L.R. and Ferguson, M.A., 2019. Bridging transformational leadership, transparent communication, and employee openness to change: The mediating role of trust. *Public relations review*, 45(3), p.101779. Available at: https://e-tarjome.com/storage/panel/fileuploads/2019-09-17/1568720817_E13508-e-tarjome.pdf
- [51] Ziaei, M., Choobineh, A., Abdoli-Eramaki, M., Ghaem, H. and Jaber, O., 2019. Psychological and physical job demands, decision latitude, and work-related social support among Iranian waste collectors. *Waste Management*, 95, pp.377-387. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0956053X19304106>.